

ODU: Open DSRC Unit toward Effective Dissemination of V2X Applications

Salvatore Iandolo, Carlo Augusto Grazia, Martin Klapez, and Maurizio Casoni

Abstract—In the context of Intelligent Transportation Systems, a Vehicular Ad-Hoc Network provides communication among nearby vehicles and roadside infrastructure. Commercial devices enabling this type of communication via the IEEE 802.11p standard are expensive and proprietary, limiting research and independent field testing. Furthermore, as the industry is their target client, they integrate features like metal waterproof enclosures or mounting brackets, which often result in relatively cumbersome devices unable to accommodate use by vulnerable road users with limited space and weight-bearing capabilities. Aiming to address these concerns, this paper presents a low-cost and open-source device assembled with off-the-shelf components, which we named Open DSRC Unit or ODU in short. The design minimizes the steps required to implement the unit while maintaining a degree of flexibility for potential extension with future upgrades. As a result, the device can act as both a RoadSide Unit and an On-Board Unit, leaving open the possibility of implementing custom messages and acting with custom roles.

Index Terms—IEEE 802.11p, ITS, OBU, ODU, Raspberry Pi, V2X

I. INTRODUCTION

In a road traffic scenario, cooperative Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication units and Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) stations can be implemented as On-Board Units (OBUs) and RoadSide Units (RSUs) in vehicles and traffic infrastructure to exchange data with each other via a short-range ad-hoc network. OBUs communicate data such as their position, speed, and driving direction multiple times per second. Additionally, they send out event-triggered messages in particular cases, such as road accidents, emergency brakings, slippery roads, etc. The physical layer standard used by WiFi-based V2X applications is IEEE 802.11p, a wireless technology that allows vehicles to communicate with their immediate surroundings such as other vehicles, roadside infrastructure, pedestrians, and other sources. As faster access to the physical medium has been the original primary motivation for the design of IEEE 802.11p, the protocol does not perform the usual WiFi authentication procedures. In addition, it includes other changes to meet the challenges of high-speed mobile

radio environments, such as strong Doppler shifts and mutable multipath conditions. The exchange of data between nodes happens without establishing a Basic Service Set (BSS). To do that, IEEE 802.11p stations use a wildcard BSSID (a value of all 1s) in the frames' header so they can start exchanging messages as soon as they are generated and enqueued for transmission. These messages are standardized to be sent on the 5.9 GHz frequency band, usually in broadcast.

Many vehicle manufacturers and industry players work in V2X research, such as Volkswagen, Toyota Motors, Qualcomm, LG Electronics, Huawei, Cisco/Cohda Wireless, and Autotalks. However, few platforms are available, and the price is high. In addition, the majority of available solutions are sold as black-box, custom configurations, making any modification or addition difficult, if not forbidden. Recently, the U.S. Department of Transportation released a national deployment plan for V2X technologies to reduce death and serious injuries on roadways [1], which is a plan to accelerate V2X deployment to embrace both vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), e.g., pedestrians, bicycles, e-scooters, and motorbikes.

With this goal in mind, this paper presents a cost-effective V2X platform using a Raspberry Pi 5 as a small, open, and portable single-board computer combined with a Mini PCI Express board and an Atheros ath9k WiFi card that allows operations on the 5.9 GHz band. The operating system is the Raspberry Pi OS, a Unix-like operating system based on the Debian Linux distribution for the Raspberry Pi family, on which the IEEE 802.11p standard was integrated through several patches. The whole setup can be accessed and replicated from the project repository¹.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II overviews related works. Section III presents the hardware platform, while Section IV details its configuration. Section V presents and analyzes the results, while Section VI concludes the article.

II. RELATED WORKS

Few works have led to the creation of open-source solutions that can operate at ITS frequencies. For example, Raviglione et al. in [2] created a Linux-based, up-to-date, open-source platform for the evaluation of IEEE 802.11p compatible Network Interface Cards, following the first cost-effective hardware implementation proposed in [3]. They developed this solution using APU1D embedded boards with the Unex DHXA-222, a WiFi PCIe module based on the AR9462 chipset with the

S. Iandolo, C.A. Grazia, M. Klapez, and M. Casoni are with the Department of Engineering *Enzo Ferrari*, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, via Pietro Vivarelli, 10, 41125, Modena, Italy (e-mail: {carloaugusto.grazia, salvatore.iandolo, martin.klapez, maurizio.casoni}@unimore.it).

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¹<https://github.com/SalvatoreIandolo/ODU-V2X/tree/main>

Fig. 1: MiniPCI Express HAT | AR9580 Wi-fi card.

usual 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz dual-band support and a declared transmission power of 17 dBm. The software platform is OpenWrt, optimal for networking and embedded devices. Despite its open-source premises, the setup shows its early limitations. For instance, the device needs to be manually patched to support the IEEE 802.11p standard. Moreover, the APU board is prohibitive in size; it is expensive and has now been discontinued, which makes us believe it is not suitable for mass deployment and for VRUs' future applications.

Along with this device, in [4], the same authors presented Oscar, an open-source, ETSI-compliant C-ITS stack for embedded hardware devices capable of managing, sending, and receiving vehicular messages. It supports the full basic services for Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs) and Vulnerable Awareness Messages (VAMs), with the intention to expand this support to Decentralized Environmental Notification Messages (DENMs), Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Messages (IVIMs), Cooperative Perception Messages (CPMs), and to security headers and certificate formats. Oscar is a software solution that is fully compatible and usable in our ODU, but as it rigorously follows the ETSI standard, it prevents working in the absence of GPS and with custom messages, which are features that we seek for research purposes.

Another approach has been the adaptation of programmable router boards to make them act as RSUs or OBUs at or near the 5.9 GHz frequency band. For example, we previously used this approach in [5], [6] to perform field tests for various purposes. An advantage of these systems is the possibility of setting higher transmission powers to test safety-critical applications with appropriate equivalent isotropic radiated power values, but the boards are somewhat big enough to be carried by. A similar approach focused on Software Defined Radio (SDR) devices [7] with the goal of assessing the performance of IEEE 802.11p technology from the radio domain. Other contributions like [8] point in the same direction, where the authors followed a Hardware in the Loop (HiL) approach to include the real 802.11p wireless hop in a simulated platform. The goal was to mitigate the gap between large field tests, reproducibility, and controllability, particularly for the automotive domain ECU integration test.

Continuing, an open or reliable RSU/OBU is not the only need; a milestone in the V2X domain is also to mitigate the gap between simulations and real field tests. Authors in [9] recognized that the high cost and reasonably low availability

of off-the-shelf devices are limiting the scientific contributions involving IEEE 802.11p vehicular networks with simulations. Their contribution is, indeed, to test real commercial equipment and provide the performance gap between real devices and simulations, unveiling the inaccuracy of famous network simulations with respect to maximum range, moderate speed impact, and the weak correlation between the PIR and PDR. This last contribution highlights the need to perform real tests with open hardware and software devices, which is of paramount importance, and we believe this is a research area enabled by our ODU contribution.

It is also a matter of applications and services that researchers want to test on top of IEEE 802.11p networks. It is the case of [10] where the authors provide a real performance evaluation of video transmission over IEEE 802.11p for assisted driving; unfortunately, there are no details about the hardware and software used to reproduce the results, in particular for the OBU/RSU forwarding hop, without specifying if the stack used is ETSI or TCP/IP, which low-level characteristics of the 11p technology are deployed and which bandwidth, frequencies, power or modulations are deployed. This is an example of a real test that can be reproduced with ODU maintaining an open dissemination. A similar but older contribution has been provided in [11] using Componentality FlexRoad devices for implementing a DSRC wireless hop. The same authors claim they did not test the compliance of the commercial device with the FlexRoad DSRC and the IEEE 802.11p standard, treating the hop as a black box without the possibility of optimizing, verifying, or validating the results.

III. HARDWARE PLATFORM

Our goal was to create a hardware platform for vehicular communications with the following requirements: IEEE 802.11p standard support, reception and transmission of ETSI ITS-G5 messages, ability to work as both a Road Side Unit (RSU) and On Board Unit (OBU), off-the-shelf components, low-cost, handy, and ready to use.

To meet these requirements, we chose the Raspberry Pi 5 Model B as the single-board computer, equipped with an Arm Cortex-A76 CPU, 8 GB of LPDDR4 RAM, and 128 GB of flash memory. The board is powered by 5V/5A DC via USB-C and has a PCIe 2.0 interface for fast peripherals. This is very convenient as it allows the addition of multiple types of Hardware Attached on Top (HAT) add-ons to expand

Fig. 2: Linux wireless subsystem schema.

the board functionalities through a standardized format, e.g., M.2. SSDs to speed up read/write operations. In our case, we added a PCIe HAT to install a Wi-Fi card that is suitable for our requirements. As depicted in Figure 1, we selected the Mikrotik R11E-5HND, an 802.11a/n adapter based on the Qualcomm Atheros AR9580 chipset and equipped with a thermal heat sink. The chip supports communications in the upper 5 GHz band as well as ath9k, a Linux kernel driver that can be easily patched to support V2X communications through the IEEE 802.11p standard. The cost of the setup is around 150 EUR (approximately 160 USD at current exchange rates), which is very cheap compared to similar equipment, both commercial and non-commercial.

IV. SOFTWARE SETUP

The Raspberry Pi 5 runs the Raspberry Operating System (OS), a Unix-like operating system based on the Debian Linux distribution explicitly designed and optimized for the Raspberry Pi platform. As mentioned in the Introduction, IEEE 802.11p devices must use a wildcard BSSID in their frames' header without establishing BSSs. This behavior is formally defined as Outside the Context of a BSS (OCB), a specific operation mode required for any 11p-compliant device. OCB mode does not need authentication, encryption, or association; the only parameters to set are the central channel frequency and bandwidth.

To implement the IEEE 802.11p communication protocol, the OS needs to be patched to make the network card operate in OCB mode in the 5.9 GHz band with a 10 MHz channel width. The device has a built-in WiFi and Bluetooth adapter working in the regular 2.4 and 5 GHz frequency bands, which we switched off at the hardware level to enable the detection of our WiFi card via the PCIe interface. However, the PCIe interface is, by default, disabled when booting the Raspberry, so this is another modification that is required to detect the Atheros WiFi card. This was done very easily by adding a couple of commands to the file `/boot/firmware/config.txt`².

Figure 2 reports the Linux wireless subsystem. The device driver, in this case ATH9K, directly interacts with the

hardware, translating high-level instructions into hardware-specific actions and vice versa. The device driver also interacts with the kernel networking stack through the MAC80211 framework, which handles MAC layer functions. MAC80211 is given directives by CFG80211, a *kernel-space* API to handle configuration logic and device management (e.g., scanning, setting up connections, power management) which, in turn, exposes functionalities to NL80211, a *user-space* API that allows user-space software and tools (e.g., iw, the NL80211-based CLI network configuration utility replacing iwconfig) to interact with wireless devices.

The steps to add support to the IEEE 802.11p protocol require several patches, each of which acts on different elements of the Linux wireless subsystem.

The first patch is specific to the ath9k³ driver and extends operations in the 5.9 GHz band (from 5.850 GHz to 5.925 GHz) for a total bandwidth of 75 MHz. This band is divided into seven channels of 10 MHz each, one of which is called the control channel (CCH), while the others are service channels. While European and American standards differ slightly on which channel is the CCH and how receivers are supposed to tune to these channels, in both cases, the CCH is the default, and it is reserved for network coordination (e.g., resource reservation, control, and management messages) and high-priority safety messages. It is important to mention that this patch also removes the flag "NO IR," a restriction present in almost all 5 GHz frequencies, blocking the possibility of initiating radiation on those frequencies.

In order to introduce in the OS regulatory information on the newly added IEEE 802.11p 5.9 GHz band, we need to update the Linux package wireless-regdb, regulatory.bin, and regulatory.db are the files used by the Linux wireless subsystem to maintain its regulatory database information. regulatory.bin is read by crda upon a Linux kernel's request for regulatory information regarding a specific country code. regulatory.db is a recent, extensible database format which, since the 4.15 Linux kernel, is directly read as a firmware file. The regulatory database is kept in a small binary format for size and code efficiency. The regulatory.bin can be parsed and read in human format by using the regdbdump command. We added a custom domain for IEEE 802.11p jamming experiments so it can only be used in isolated environments for research purposes. This patch also modifies drivers to allow the user to set regulatory domains (NL80211-REGDOM-SET-BY-DRIVER vs. NL80211-REGDOM-SET-BY-USER), which is, by default, set by the driver itself. This is crucial to shift the Linux wireless regulatory database to a specific country code where DSRC channels are enabled. Regarding OCB, this patch also allows the scanning of devices set in OCB mode, which is, by default, disabled. After the new regulatory domain is created, it needs to be signed with the Central Regulatory Domain Agent (CRDA). CRDA is a userspace agent responsible for reading and understanding regulatory.bin and updating regulatory domains. CRDA is intended to be triggered by uevents from the kernel (via

³While the Atheros drivers have evolved over the years, the latter versions (e.g., ath10k, ath11k) limit their extensibility. Luckily, the ath5k and ath9k drivers still allow a greater degree of configuration.

²The commands are documented in the project repository.

udev) upon changes in the regulatory domain and setting up the new regulations. Nowadays, it's no longer needed as of kernel v.4.15; the regulatory database is read by the Linux kernel directly as a firmware file during boot. The integrity of regulatory.db is typically ensured by the regulatory daemon by verifying the built-in RSA signature against a list of public keys in a preconfigured directory.

The default compilers and linkers distributed with an OS are configured to build executables to run on that OS, typically for a specific CPU architecture. Native builds use these default compilers and linkers. Cross-compilation is the process of building code for a target other than the one running the build process. Considering the hardware specifications of the Raspberry, the native build was our choice. After applying the patches, installing the modules, and rebooting the system, the device is ready to work on ITS frequencies. When the device boots up, an automated script is executed to configure the device in OCB mode and operate in the 5.9 GHz frequency band. This script does, in order, bring the wireless interface down, set the regulatory domain to "country" x (which is the one specific for ITS frequencies), set OCB as the interface type, bring the wireless interface back up, set the wireless frequency band to 5.9 GHz with 10 MHz wide channels, assign the IP address to the wireless interface, create a new wireless interface in monitor mode, and bring the monitor wireless interface up.

```
$ sudo ip link set wlan0 down
$ sudo iw dev wlan0 set type ocb
$ sudo ip link set wlan0 up
$ sudo iw dev wlan0 ocb join 5900 10MHZ
$ sudo ip address add 10.1.1.1/24 brd +
dev wlan0
$ sudo iw dev wlan0 interface add wlan1
type monitor
$ sudo ifconfig wlan1 up
```

Listing 1: 802.11p and OCB mode setup.

The ISO linked in the project repository is ready to use, and the whole setup has already been implemented; it just needs to be flashed without any further configuration required.

V. TEST RESULTS

The first test we conducted was to ensure that the device was effectively transmitting on the 5.9 GHz frequency band. To do so, we used GNU Radio, which is a free and open-source signal processing software development toolkit, combined with the Software-Defined Radio (SDR) board USRP B210, which provides a fully integrated, single-board platform with continuous frequency coverage from 70 MHz to 6 GHz. Our script allowed us to tune the SDR on channel 180, i.e., the CCH in the 5.9 GHz frequency band, in monitor mode. The detected packets were then saved locally for post-processing. Figure 3 shows the signal detected by the SDR coming from an ODU sending ICMP messages.

The next step was to check whether the ODU could correctly decode ITS messages coming from real RSUs. We used Movyon Electronics commercial devices as RSUs, which

have EN 302 636-4-1 compliant GeoNetworking and transport layer stacks. These RSUs implement an HTTP/HTTPs server, providing a set of different APIs for the transmission and reception of Facility Layer messages such as CAM, DENM, and SPATEM. The test environment involved 2 Movyon RSUs and one ODU. The RSUs were set to send CAMs and DENMs, while the ODU listened for messages on the monitor wireless interface. Through tshark, a packet-capturing tool used on the ODU that is part of the network protocol analyzer software Wireshark, the messages sent by the RSUs were correctly visible on the terminal, as shown below.

```
$ sudo tshark -i wlan1
$ Capturing on 'wlan1'
1 0.000000000 0.15.0.b4:b5:b6:c4:11:49
-> Broadcast CAM 166 CAM
2 0.551939018 0.15.0.b4:b5:b6:c4:11:49
-> Broadcast CAM 166 CAM
3 1.095924462 0.15.0.b4:b5:b6:c4:11:49
-> Broadcast CAM 166 CAM
4 1.639949425 0.15.0.b4:b5:b6:c4:11:49
-> Broadcast CAM 166 CAM
5 2.187944499 0.15.0.b4:b5:b6:c4:11:49
-> Broadcast CAM 166 CAM
```

Listing 2: CAM/DENM detection.

Following these preliminary tests, we deployed our ODU in field tests by installing it in a test car equipped with a regular power socket. As such an arrangement was available, we powered the ODU through the car instead of using a battery pack. Antennas were placed on the vehicle roof to increase the reception signal range. The vehicle was then driven around with the goal of catching ITS packets from other vehicles traveling on the roads. As few vehicles are equipped with IEEE 802.11p hardware, we preferably travel on or near motorways and ring roads, where vehicle density in time is higher than in an urban setting. The received packets were then saved locally on the ODU and ready for post-processing. The .pcap files were subsequently parsed, and the CAM information was extracted through a web application developed using Python and Flask. Each CAM was filtered by the *stationID* field, which is an anonymized vehicle identifier. *stationID* was then associated with various packets containing data such

Fig. 3: SDR signal on channel 180 for ODU messages.

Fig. 4: CAM vehicle trace from ODU.

as longitude, latitude, speed, heading, and timestamp. These are only the most relevant information, but more data can be extracted. As shown in Figure 4, the web app is able to plot the selected vehicle route on a map, giving concrete information about its movement for as long as the ODU received CAMs. This can be done with DENMs as well, displaying information about the event and its location.

As the last test, we sent custom ODU CAMs, DENMs, and GeoNetworking messages from the ODU, checking whether both Movyon RSUs and other ODUs correctly detected them. We used Scapy, a powerful interactive packet manipulation library written in Python to create the messages. It is able to forge or decode packets of a vast number of protocols, as well as capture them. A CAM packet has several layers that need to be replicated with Scapy: Dot11, Dot11 QoS, LLC (Logical-link Control), GeoNetworking, BTP-B (Basic Transport Protocol), and, finally, the ITS payload, which contains either the DENM or CAM fields. All listed layers are stand-alone except for GeoNetworking, BTP-B, and ITS. The latter is a single payload queued to the packet after the LLC layer. The ITS payload, in our case, could be either a CAM or a DENM and was generated using the Python library `asn1tools`. As input, we gave the library a dictionary containing all of the CAM fields following the ASN.1 notation; custom values, if any, can be added at this stage. The output is a UPER-encoded string of the ITS payload. As the GeoNetworking stack is not included in Scapy, we implemented it adding the fields “Basic header”, “Common header”, and “Topologically-Scoped Broadcast Packet”. The packets are sent on channel 180 every 100ms, and we confirmed that the RSUs were able to detect the packets and decode them correctly.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the Open DSRC Unit (ODU), a low-cost and open-source platform for Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs) that supports IEEE 802.11p communication. The device addresses critical barriers in Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) research, including high costs and the proprietary nature of existing solutions. Utilizing off-the-shelf components, such as the Raspberry Pi 5 and the Mikrotik R11E-5HND Wi-Fi card, the ODU provides a flexible, portable solution for both research and practical deployment. Its capability to act as both a Road Side Unit (RSU) and an On-Board

Unit (OBU) facilitates a wide range of V2X applications and performance assessments.

Experimental validation showed the successful integration of IEEE 802.11p, including robust reception and transmission of Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs) and Decentralized Environmental Notification Messages (DENMs). Field tests confirmed the ODU’s ability to interact seamlessly with commercial RSUs and other ODUs, highlighting its potential for realistic V2X system testing. Furthermore, its design supports the generation of custom ITS messages, enhancing its utility in exploring innovative applications beyond current standards.

By combining cost-effectiveness, ease of assembly, and adaptability, the ODU platform lowers the barrier to ITS research, promoting broader participation and accelerating innovation in V2X technology. Future research could leverage ODU’s open design for extended applications, including advanced safety systems, Vulnerable Road User (VRU) integration, and further exploration of GeoNetworking capabilities.

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